

EFFECT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PUPILS AT PORT AREA ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The primary purpose of this study is to determine the effect of socio-economic status on the academic performance of pupils at Port Area Elementary School, Jolo II District. Moreover, the study aims to assess the level of academic performance of these pupils and identify the social and economic factors affecting it. Additionally, the study seeks to establish measures that can be implemented to improve their academic performance. This study used a descriptive research survey design, employing questionnaires, document reviews, and interviews to collect data. The findings of this study revealed that the majority of intermediate pupils at Port Area Elementary School achieved a satisfactory proficiency level and acknowledged that their academic performance is influenced by socio-economic factors. The social factors identified as significant predictors of academic performance include peer group influence, work at home, lack of proper guidance at home, lack of parental care, lack of self-motivation, lack of sense of belongingness, and school attendance. The economic factors identified as significant predictors of academic performance include parents having no source of income, growing family size, lack of provision of school supplies and other learning materials, and the distance to school. Furthermore, the advisers of these intermediate pupils have identified some appropriate measures to address the social and economic factors and ultimately improve academic performance. In conclusion, the majority of pupils agreed that satisfactory academic performance is affected by social and economic factors. The effect of these factors is significant at the 0.01 level of confidence in the regression analysis. To improve academic performance, class advisers suggested increasing the financial assistance from the government to the school and pupils,

improving teaching resources, and encouraging parental participation to motivate their children to engage in school activities.

Keywords: *Socio-economic status, Academic performance, Intermediate pupils*

INTRODUCTION

Understanding the effects of socio-economic status on academic performance is important in determining effective and valid teaching and learning strategies. Determining the relation between these two variables is important for all educators, so that majority of the students can achieve to their academic potential (Tomaszewski et al., 2020). By doing so, it can assist educators in determining instructional strategies that best fit every students. In this study, the researcher analyzed the effects of socio-economic status on the academic performance of elementary grade level because education is the most important weapon to bring changes in the society by making people wise and rational. It is the prime equipment to make the people of a country like Philippines skilled and civilized through individual development. Without educated citizen, no country can make progress (Rosalina, 2023). The whole process of educating individual is focused on academic performance and this is very much influenced by the socio-economic status of parents, the environment and many more. It is education that determines an individual occupation, income, status or position in the society.

Socio-economic status is related to school performance; it does not mean that the rich are born smart. This only means that, in richer families, children are more likely to have more experiences that stimulate their intellectual development (Lurie et al., 2021). Also, many educators think that low economic status creates a negative effect on academic performance. A study by Vadivel et al. (2023) found that children from low socio-economic backgrounds do not perform as well as they potentially could at school compared to children from high socio-economic backgrounds. Most studies, however, compare pupils from across all socio-economic backgrounds to reach the conclusion that low socio-economic status adversely affects a range of educational outcomes. Another important dimension, however, is the factors that may influence educational outcomes within particular SES bands. One of the most debated issues among educational professionals is the relationship between the academic achievement and socio-economic status of pupils. A prevalent argument is that the socioeconomic status of a student has a major effect on his/her academic achievement. Many educators think that low socio-economic status creates a negative effect on academic achievement.

Hoffman and Miller (2020) mentioned that the basic needs of certain student are not being met, thus not allowing the students to physically or mentally be able to perform in school. If student are not properly fed or given proper hygiene care, they cannot be expected to perform successfully in their academics. On the contrary, there are also many who feel that socio economic status is the key factor in academic performance. Munir et al. (2023) concluded that socio-economic status and poverty in school districts are not an

excuse for low academic performance in students, but a condition. “Like gravity, it affects everything”.

There have been many studies that sought to examine socio-economic factors affecting academic performance of pupils but it varies greatly from places to places. Most of these studies have focused on pupil’s performance in urban areas; countries that tend to have large difference in socio-economic status also have large difference in school achievement (Ndemwa & Ngesu, 2021). However, since Sulu environment is different in terms of culture, educational status and school environment, it is very important to examine the relevance of these factors in Sulu context.

Academic performances of pupils are measured through their written task and performance tasks; it provides them the means to show their abilities and skills, to express their ideas and their selves accurately. Most of the time, good or bad grades are largely affected by the kind of socio-economic status they are into. With the assumption that, the socio-economic status has great effect on the academic performance of pupils, it is within this context that the researcher decides to conduct an investigation about the effect of socio-economic status on the academic performance of pupils at Port Area Elementary School. It is very evident that the quality of parents and home background of a pupil in this school goes a long way to predict the quality and regularity of the satisfaction and provision of a child’s functional survival and academic needs. Poor parental care with gross deprivation of social and economic needs of a child usually yield poor academic performance of the child. Similarly, good parenting supported by strong economic home background could enhance strong academic performance of the child. This further predicts academic performance of these pupils in national examinations.

Research Questions

In Sulu, educational researchers and practitioners as well as parents and other education stakeholders have expressed increasing concerns about the academic performance of pupils in elementary level particularly in Jolo, considering that it is the very basic foundation of children’s education growth. Low academic performance constitutes a problem that needs attention. In Jolo II District the quality of pupils’ learning is still a major problem. Data from the result of National Achievement Test reveals that pupils from schools in Sulu lag behind in academic achievement, and therefore implies that few get access to good learning situations, perhaps there could be an effect of socio-economic status or background of pupils to their academic performance. Thus, this study aimed to determine effect of socio-economic status on pupils’ academic performance at Port Area Elementary School.

1. What is the level of academic performance of pupils at Port Area Elementary School?
2. What social factors affect pupils’ academic performance at Port Area Elementary School?
3. What economic factors affect pupils’ academic performance at Port Area Elementary School?

4. What measures can be put in place to improve pupils' performance at Port Area Elementary School?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive research survey design. Said method is considered apt because it enables the researcher to generate information from the respondents through research instruments based on well-defined concepts and related variables (Talikan, 2021; Ajan et al., 2024). According to Somasundaran (2022), it intends to present facts about the nature and status of a situation as it exists at the time of the study. In addition, it also concerns with the relationships and practices that exist, beliefs and processes that are on-going, effects that are being felt or trends that are developing (Dubey & Kothari, 2022; Talikan, 2022). Therefore, it can be helpful in order to describe the current conditions and situations based on the impressions and perceptions of the respondents of the study (Somasundaran, 2022). The design was therefore appropriate for this study since the researcher gathered information without manipulation of variables.

Locale of the Study

The study was carried out at Port Area Elementary School, Jolo II District located at Port Area, Walled City, Jolo, Sulu. The study area was chosen because it is located near the barangay Bus-Bus where most of the children of the residence considered having low economic status. Therefore, it was very imperative to conduct a study to find out to what extent is the effect of the two variables exists. Research has been done on academic achievement but not specifically in this study area.

Respondents of the Study

The target respondents for this study were the intermediate grade level which are Grade IV, V and VI, each grade level consist of three (3) sections with 55 maximum number of pupils. This study utilized 180 intermediate pupils to answer the research questionnaire randomly selected from the sections. The class advisers are also utilized as the key respondents in each grade level.

Research Instruments

The study utilized questionnaires and document review to collect data.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire was used for data collection because as Kiess and Bloomquist (1985) observe, questionnaires offer considerable advantage in administration, presents an even stimulus potentiality to large numbers of people simultaneously and provides the

investigation with an easy accumulation of data. Srivastava (2024) maintains that questionnaires give respondents freedom to express their views or opinion and also to make suggestions. It's on the basis of these strengths that the instrument was chosen. Questionnaires will be distributed to pupils to elicit information on the study objectives. The questionnaires contain sections that gathered information on social and economic factors affecting pupil's academic performance at Port Area Elementary School. Parent's income, education and occupation were used to measure the economic status of the family. The questionnaires contained both open and closed ended questions.

Document Review

The researcher also collected data pertaining to the examination results by looking at the records of the student's academic achievement earned from first and third Quarter. This was necessary as it enabled the researcher to collate the information given by the student and that captured by the researcher.

Interview Method

The researcher also used interview method to teachers/advisers who are considered well-versed on the issue of pupils academic performance.

Sampling Procedure

Sampling design is the method a researcher applied to determine the members or items of the target population to be included in the study. Mugenda and Mugenda (1999) recommend a representative sample of 10-30% for descriptive survey research. Therefore a representative sample of 20 pupils were selected using simple random sampling from the 55 total numbers of pupils in each grade level section accounting for 30% representation. To obtain the pupils that participated in the study, a list of names of pupils in the selected grade level in the study locale formed a sampling frame from which the researcher obtained through simple random sampling. The sample size for the study will be 180 pupils.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents

Grade level			Section
IV	V	VI	
20	20	20	A
20	20	20	B
20	20	20	C
60	60	60	120

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher sent a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Sulu Division, to the Jolo II district head as well as the school principal asking for a permit to conduct the study then set a schedule with the respondents to administer the

questionnaires. The researcher personally administered the instruments to all the respondents who were given 3 days to complete all the items adequately, after which the researcher collected the filled-in questionnaires. The data for this study were collected within a period of one week.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

This study employed descriptive statistics to analyze the data obtained. Questionnaires were checked to remove those with incomplete items and outliers. This research yielded data that required both qualitative and quantitative analysis. Quantitative analysis entails analyzing numbers about a situation by choosing specific aspects of that situation. Descriptive statistics that will include percentage and frequency counts were used to analyze the data obtained. The data obtained were reported and discussed thematically in line with the objectives of the study.

Table 2. Statistical Tools

Statement of the Problem	Statistical Tools
What is the level of academic performance of pupil's at Port Area Elementary School?	Weighted Mean
What social factors affect pupil's academic performance at Port Area Elementary School?	Weighted Mean & Regression
What economic factors affect pupil's academic performance at Port Area Elementary School?	Weighted Mean & Regression
What measures can be put in place to improve pupil's performance at Port Area Elementary School?	Interview

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the discussion of the results of this study. The arrangement of the discussion followed the sequence of the research questions found in the statement of the problems.

The first research question is “What is the level of academic performance of intermediate pupils at Port Area Elementary School?” This problem can be answered using the average percentage grades of the intermediate pupils at Port Area Elementary School. Table 3.1a shows the percent distribution of the pupils grouped according to the standard proficiency levels used in the DepEd. 180 intermediate pupils (grades IV, V, and VI) randomly selected from sections A, B, and C. 32.2 percent of the intermediate pupils achieved the proficiency level fairly satisfactory, 27.8 percent achieve the satisfactory level, 23.3 percent achieved the very satisfactory level and 16.7 percent achieved the outstanding level of proficiency. The data shows that all of the intermediate pupils have passed the teaching and learning standard of the teachers in Port Area Elementary School. Unfortunately, the majority of the pupils is in fairly satisfactory proficiency level.

TABLE 3.1a
PERCENT DISTRIBUTION OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
OF INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

Proficiency Levels	Frequency	Percent
75-79 (Fairly Satisfactory)	58	32.2
80-84 (Satisfactory)	50	27.8
85-89 (Very Satisfactory)	42	23.3
90-100 (Outstanding)	30	16.7
Total	180	100.0

Table 3.1b shows the proficiency level distributed according to year levels. The mean and standard deviation shows that the grade IV pupils achieved the satisfactory level at mean and standard deviation 3.13 and 1.033 respectively, the grade V pupils achieved the satisfactory level at mean and standard deviation 3.27 and standard deviation respectively and the grade VI pupils achieved the satisfactory level at mean 3.33 and 1.098 respectively. The overall mean of the total intermediate pupils achieved the satisfactory proficiency level at mean and standard deviation 3.24 and .081 respectively. The data in this study indicates that the intermediate pupils at Port Area Elementary School achieved the satisfactory proficiency level. This level of proficiency implies that the pupils satisfactorily achieved much of the minor objectives and achieved less of the major objectives. However, the general information implies that these students have passed in the evaluation processes conducted by their teachers in all subject areas offered for the intermediate pupils.

TABLE 3.1b
DISTRIBTUION OF MEAN GRADES BY YEAR LEVELS

Grade Levels	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Grade IV	60	3.13	1.033	Satisfactory
Grade V	60	3.27	1.119	Satisfactory
Grade VI	60	3.33	1.098	Satisfactory
Total	180	3.24	1.081	Satisfactory

Legend: 1.0-1.49 [1] =Below-74(Did not meet Expectation); 1.5-2.49 [2]=75-79(Fairly Satisfactory); 2.5-3.49 [3]=80-84 (Satisfactory); .5-4.49 [4] = 85-89 (Very Satisfactory); 4.5-5.0 [5] = 90-Above (Outstanding)

Table 3.1c shows the F values for analysis of the mean difference when the intermediate pupils are grouped according to year levels. The F values .509 with significant values .602 greater than .05 level of significance indicates that the proficiency levels of the intermediate pupils do not differ significantly when the grades are grouped according to year levels. The data implies that the teachers in the grades IV, V and VI have taught the subjects in class with the same or almost the same standards of teaching and evaluation processes. The teachers should improve a little more their standardized teaching and evaluation processes to improve the proficiency level of the intermediate pupils or a little increased the average percentage grades of the intermediate pupils to cope with the proficiency level in the national standards.

TABLE 3.1c
ANOVA TABLE FOR DIFFERENCE OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE GROUPED
ACCORDING TO GRADE LEVELS

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.>.05
Grades * Grade Levels	Between Groups (Combined)	1.197	2	.598	.509	.602
	Within Groups	208.048	177	1.175		
	Total	209.244	179			

The second research question is “What social factors affect pupils’ academic performance at Port Area Elementary School?” The 180 intermediate pupils were given research questionnaire to survey the social factors affecting their academic performance. Table 3.2a shows the mean and standard deviation of the pupils’ responses. The intermediate pupils agree that “Number of negative situations at home,” “No self-motivation,” “Work at home,” “Attendance in school,” “No sense of belongingness,” “Parents’ attitude towards education,” while they moderately agree to the indicators like “Health problems,” “Lack of parental care,” “No proper guidance at home,” and “Peer group influence” are some social factors that can affect their academic performance. The overall mean 3.52 and standard deviation 1.138 given the verbal description agree. The data indicates that the intermediate pupils agree that their performance is affected by the social factors.

TABLE 3.2a
SOCIAL FACTORS AS PERCEIVED BY INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

	Mean	SD	Description
1. Number of negative situations at home	3.79	1.097	Agree
2. No self-motivation	3.62	1.114	Agree
3. Work at home	3.61	1.090	Agree
4. Attendance in school	3.60	1.141	Agree
5. No sense of belongingness	3.59	1.142	Agree
6. Parents’ attitude towards education	3.55	1.074	Agree
7. Health problems	3.49	1.096	Moderately Agree
8. Lack of parental care	3.44	1.260	Moderately Agree
9. No proper guidance at home	3.29	1.310	Moderately Agree
10. Peer group influence	3.23	1.061	Moderately Agree
N = 180	3.52	1.138	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49=Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49=Disagree; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Agree; 3.5-4.49=Agree; 4.5-5.0=Strongly Agree

Table 3.2b shows regression model summary for analysis of the factors affecting the academic performance of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School. The regression values .948 and the regression square values .899 indicates that about 89.9 percent of the factors are accounted by the model as social factors that can affect the academic performance of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School. The Predictor variables (Constant) are Attendance in school, No proper guidance at home, No sense of belongingness, Number of negative situations at home, Peer group

influence, No self-motivation, Health problems, and Parents' attitude towards education, Lack of parental care, and Work at home. The dependent variables are average percentile grades of the intermediate pupils.

TABLE 3.2b
REGRESSION MODEL SUMMAY FOR THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL
FACTORS ON THE ACADMIC PERFORMANCE OF
THE INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.948 ^a	.899	.893	.354

Table 3.2c shows the F values 150.103 with significant values .000 less than .01 level of significance, for the effect of social factors on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils. The data suggests that the effect of social factors on the academic performance is significant at .01 significant level of confidence. The data indicates that the social factors can significantly affect the academic performance of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School.

TABLE 3.2c
F-VALUES FOR THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL FACTORS ON ACADEMC
PERFORMANCE OF THE INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	188.070	10	18.807	150.103	.000 ^b
Residual	21.175	169	.125		
Total	209.244	179			

a. Dependent Variable: Grades

b. Predictors: (Constant), Attendance in school, No proper guidance at home, No sense of belongingness , Number of negative situations at home, Peer group influence, No self-motivation, Health problems, Parents' attitude towards education, Lack of parental care, Work at home

Table 3.2d shows that the t-values with significant values less than .05 significant level of confidence are social factors that can significantly predict the effect on the academic performance. The social factors that are good predictor of the effect on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils are Peer group influence, Work at home, No proper guidance at home, Lack of parental care, No self-motivation, No sense of belongingness, and Attendance in school.

TABLE 3.2d
T-VALUES FOR PREDICTOR VARIABLES (SOCIAL FACTORS) AND INDEPENDENT
VARIABLES GRADES OF THE INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

Model 1	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.	Sig <.05
	Coefficients B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta			
(Constant)	.086	.131		.655	.513	
Peer group influence	.354	.073	.348	4.828	.000	Significant
Work at home	.222	.103	.224	2.163	.032	Significant

No proper guidance at home	.215	.055	.260	3.909	.000	Significant
Lack of parental care	.220	.085	.257	2.586	.011	Significant
No self-motivation	-.252	.080	-.260	-3.168	.002	Significant
Parents' attitude towards education	.022	.092	.022	.237	.813	Not Significant
No sense of belongingness	.496	.070	.523	7.065	.000	Significant
Number of negative situations at home	.028	.068	.029	.419	.675	Not Significant
Health problems	-.022	.077	-.022	-.282	.778	Not Significant
Attendance in school	-.342	.095	-.361	-3.599	.000	Significant

Synthesis

The social factors that are good predictor of the effect on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils are Peer group influence, Work at home, No proper guidance at home, Lack of parental care, No self-motivation, No sense of belongingness, and Attendance in school.

The scatterplot in figure 2 shows the linear relationship of the regressed social factors and academic performance of the intermediate pupils. The plot shows linearly significant effect of regressed social factors on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils using their percent average grades as indicator.

Figure 1. Scatterplot for Regressed Values Social Factors and Academic Performance of Intermediate Pupils

The third research question is “What economic factors affect pupils’ academic performance at Port Area Elementary School?” The 180 intermediate pupils were given research questionnaire to survey the economic factors affecting their academic performance. Table 3.3a shows the mean and standard deviation of the pupils’ responses. The intermediate pupils agree that “Financial burden/worries of parents”, “Low family income”, “Parents do not give any amount when going to school”, “Parents low educational attainment”, “School fees and other monetary contributions”, “Parents have no source of living”, “School supplies and other learning materials are not provided”, “Family size is growing bigger”, “Going to school without taking meals”, while they moderately agree to the “Distance of school”. The overall mean 3.52 and standard deviation 1.138 given the verbal description Agree. Interpreting the whole economic factors, the data indicates that the pupils agree that social factors can affect their academic performance.

TABLE 3.3a
ECONOMIC FACTORS AS PERCEIVED BY INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

	Mean	SD	Description
1. Financial burden/worries of parents	4.47	.794	Agree
2. Low family income	4.38	.806	Agree
3. Parents do not give any amount when going to school	4.21	.939	Agree
4. Parents low educational attainment	4.17	.950	Agree
5. School fees and other monetary contributions	4.10	1.047	Agree
6. Parents have no source of living	4.08	.997	Agree
7. School supplies and other learning materials are not provided	4.08	1.046	Agree
8. Family size is growing bigger	4.03	.939	Agree
9. Going to school without taking meals	3.90	1.020	Agree
10. Distance of school	3.44	1.074	Moderately Agree
N = 180	4.09	.9612	Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49=Strongly Disagree; 1.5-2.49=Disagree; 2.5-3.49=Moderately Agree; 3.5-4.49=Agree; 4.5-5.0=Strongly Agree

Table 3.3b shows regression model summary for analysis of the factors affecting the academic performance of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School. The regression values .934 and the regression square values .872 indicates that about 87.2 percent of the economic factors are accounted by the model that can affect the academic performance of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School. The Predictor variables (Constant) are Distance of school, Financial burden/worries of parents, Parents do not give any amount when going to school, Parents have no source of living, Low family income, Going to school without taking meals, School fees and other monetary contributions, Family size is growing bigger, Parents low educational attainment, School supplies and other learning materials are not provided and the dependent variables are percentile average grades of the intermediate pupils.

TABLE 3.3b
REGRESSION MODEL SUMMARY FOR THE EFFECT OF ECONOMIC
FACTORS ON THE ACADMIC PERFORMANCE OF
THE INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.934 ^a	.872	.864	.399

Table 3.3c shows the F values 114.738 with significant values .000 less than .01 level of significance, for the effect of economic factors on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils. The data suggests that the effect of economic factors on the academic performance is significant at .01 significant level of confidence. The data indicates that the social factors can significantly affect the academic performance of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School.

The dependent variable are average percentile grades of the intermediate pupils. The predictor variables (Constant) are Distance of school, Financial burden/worries of parents, Parents do not give any amount when going to school, Parents have no source of living, Low family income, Going to school without taking meals, School fees and other monetary contributions, Family size is growing bigger, Parents low educational attainment, School supplies and other learning materials are not provided.

TABLE 3.3c
F-VALUES FOR THE EFFECT OF ECONOMIC FACTORS ON ACADEMC
PERFORMANCE OF THE INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	182.381	10	18.238	114.738	.000 ^b
	Residual	26.863	169	.159		
	Total	209.244	179			

Table 3.3d shows that the t-values with significant values less than .05 significant level of confidence are economic factors that can significantly predict the effect on the academic performance. The economic factors that are good predictor of the effect on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils are “Parents have no source of living”, “Family size is growing bigger”, “School supplies and other learning materials are not provided”, “Distance of school.”

TABLE 3.3d
T-VALUES FOR PREDICTOR VARIABLES (ECONOMIC FACTORS) AND INDEPENDENT
VARIABLES GRADES OF THE INTERMEDIATE PUPILS

Model 1	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Sig < .05
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	-.029	.206		-.139	.890	
Going to school without taking meals	.154	.087	.145	1.768	.079	NS
Financial burden/worries of parents	-.120	.088	-.088	-1.369	.173	NS
Low family income	-.060	.100	-.045	-.601	.549	NS
Parents low educational attainment	.008	.113	.007	.070	.944	NS

School fees and other monetary contributions	-.043	.104	-.041	-.408	.683	NS
Parents have no source of living	.249	.125	.229	1.981	.049	S
Parents do not give any amount when going to school	-.066	.087	-.058	-.761	.448	NS
Family size is growing bigger	.466	.113	.405	4.110	.000	S
School supplies and other learning materials are not provided	-.351	.122	-.340	-2.871	.005	S
Distance of school	.707	.068	.702	10.473	.000	S

Dependent Variable: Grades

NS=Not Significant; S=Significant

Synthesis

The economic factors that are good predictor of the effect on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils are “Parents have no source of living”, “Family size is growing bigger”, “School supplies and other learning materials are not provided”, “Distance of school.”

The scatterplot in figure 3 shows the linear relationship of the regressed economic factors and academic performance of the intermediate pupils. The plot shows linearly significant effect of regressed economic factors on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils using their percent average grades as indicator.

Figure 2. Scatterplot of the Regressed Economic Factors and the Academic Performance of the Intermediate Pupils

The fourth research question is “What measures can be put in place to improve pupils’ performance at Port Area Elementary School?” This research question was answered using interview with the advisers of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School. The question being asked was “What are the possible Measures that can be put in place to improve Pupils’ Academic Performance at Port Area Elementary School?”

The discussions are presented according to the factors involved and the academic performance of the intermediate pupils.

Social Factors

The responses of the interviewed advisers on the improvement of the social factors to encounter effects on the academic performance are shown in the following table 3.4a.

TABLE 3.4a
POSSIBLE MEASURES TO OVERCOME THE
EFFECT OF SOCIAL FACTORS

<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Teachers and administrators should be provided a special training on learning strategies for students from a low socio-economic background.2. The school management should enhance guidance and counseling in schools so as to address the social and economic challenges facing the pupils.3. School administration should ensure that there are no social biases against poor pupils.
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The grade VI adviser believed that academic performance can be affected strongly by teaching strategies. They suggested that the teachers and school administrator should attain training on learning strategies to treat specifically the pupils from low socio-economic background to improve their academic performance.

The grade V adviser emphasized the needs of strengthening the guidance and counselling programs. This adviser pointed out that the school administrator or school managers should enhance guidance and counselling programs in schools to address the social and economic challenges facing the pupils. It is quietly important to provide the pupils proper motivation, especially when they are not equipped with enough skills and social capabilities to cope with the teaching strategies of teachers. So the guidance counselor can be a better mediator to fill in the gap between the teaching strategies and the social adjustment of the pupils in the classroom.

The grade IV adviser have admitted that there are social biases in treating the extremely poor pupils. Hence, commented to the status of the school administrator to help the pupils coming from very poor families. This way school social biases towards these poor pupils will be addressed.

Economic Factors

The responses of the interviewed advisers on the improvement of the economic factors to encounter effects on the academic performance are shown in the following table 3.4b.

TABLE 3.4b
POSSIBLE MEASURES TO OVERCOME THE
EFFECT OF ECONOMIC FACTORS

<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Conduct a campaign in the community to stop engaging pupils in home-related economic activities that affect academic performance negatively.2. Encourage NGOs to assist poor families so that they can educate their children.3. Strengthen the strict implementation of 4Ps Program of the DSWD which provides educational assistance to school children belonging to low income families.
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The Grade VI adviser of Port Area Elementary School have suggested to conduct community campaign to stop pupils engaged in home related economic activities that affect academic performance. This can be done through strong support to organize the Parents Teachers Association (PTA) as a mandate in the DepEd governing schools. Every school should have strong link with the parents to involve them in the school activities. The school administrator should include in the program of activities of the PTA the campaign to stop involvement of school age pupils in the home related economic activities. Many school age pupils were utilized by their parents to assist economic activities at home. This adviser has suggested to minimize the utilization of children to be involved in home related activities to improve academic performance.

The grade V adviser suggested to Encourage NGOs to assist poor families so that children can concentrate on education. Although NGOs are doing their counterparts in the development of the economic condition of the pupils. As a matter of fact, the government has already given appropriation to the school to help the pupils in the form of MOOE. However, this is not enough to maneuver the school activities.

The grade IV adviser suggested that there is a need to strengthen the strict implementation of 4Ps Program of the DSWD which provides educational assistance to school children belonging to low income families. The government has already implemented the 4Ps program, unfortunately the subsidy is not enough to cover all problems of the school children. However, everyone has to exercise its role to improve the economic condition of the people so as to improve the academic performance.

The responses of the interviewed advisers on the improvement of the academic performance are some important points of discussion. Everyone believed that academic performance is a result of several activities of teaching and learning. This study identified some social and economic factors that can affect the academic performance. The analysis of the effect of the social and economic factors discussed above have shown the significant effect of these factors on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils. The possible measures suggested by the intermediate advisers are shown in table 3.4c.

TABLE 3.4c
POSSIBLE MEASURES TO IMPROVE
ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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1. Increase of government's funding to schools to enable them acquire more instructional resources and amenities to be utilized for remedial instruction especially for pupils from low socio-economic status.
 2. Parents should be sensitive and mindful at all times about the progress of their child and must prioritize the needs of their children morally, socially and economically.
 3. Teachers should use intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in teaching to enhance participation of slow learners in class discussion.
 4. Local government should provide educational assistance to deserving elementary pupils who are belonging to poorest of the poor.
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The grade VI adviser is optimistic to say that increase of government's funding to schools to enable them acquire more instructional resources and amenities to be utilized for remedial instruction especially for pupils from low socio-economic status. In the advent of the K-12 curriculum way back 2011, the government have encountered so many problems such as increase and training of teachers, provide school resources, classrooms, etc. These problems gradually improved by the DepEd, but of course, not totally relieved. This adviser still felt the need to improve the teaching resources through the increase of school funds with the sole target of supporting the poor pupils in the conduct of the radiation program which is also implemented in many schools. However, for improvement purpose the adviser have felt to add more financial support to overcome the needs of instructional materials.

The grade V adviser have strong feeling towards the participation of the parents in order to improve the academic performance of the pupils. This adviser suggested that Parents should be sensitive and mindful at all times about the progress of their child and must prioritize the needs of their children morally, socially and economically. As an expression of love for children there is a need to have strong parental guidance, specifically on academic matters.

The adviser of the grade IV pupils has felt the needs of motivation in order to improve progress. This adviser said teachers should use intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in teaching to enhance participation of slow learners in class discussion. Teaching strategies, of course, is the most important aspect of academic performance. Good teaching strategy always provide good learning, hence improved the academic performance.

The grade VI adviser has suggested further that Local government should provide educational assistance to deserving elementary pupils who are belonging to poorest of the poor. This means that the government should award scholarship programs for those pupils who deserving. However, this suggestion has been satisfied by the new educational program of the government for "no tuition fee". The college students, high schools, and the senior high schools are now tuition free. The problems of the payments in the public schools are now quietly a good help for the poor students. Ever since. Elementary schools are free education. But, good as well when the pupils are provided

with financial assistance in the form of extrinsic motivation to excel further in their economic endeavor.

Summary of Findings

Careful analysis and interpretation of the collected data revealed the following significant findings.

1. The majority of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School achieved the satisfactory proficiency level of performance.
2. The majority of the intermediate pupils agree that academic performance is affected by the social factors. The social factors that are good predictor of the effect on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils are Peer group influence, Work at home, No proper guidance at home, Lack of parental care, No self-motivation, No sense of belongingness, and Attendance in school.
3. The majority of the pupils also agree that the academic performance is affected by the economic factors. The economic factors that are good predictor of the effect on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils are “Parents have no source of living”, “Family size is growing bigger”, “School supplies and other learning materials are not provided”, “Distance of school.”
4. The advisers of the intermediate pupils have identified some appropriate measures to encounter the social, economic factors eventually improve the academic performance. These advisers suggested to improve the government financial assistance to the school and pupils, improve school teaching resources and remediation programs, participation of the parents to motivate their children’s school activities.

The majority of the pupils agreed that academic performance is affected by the social and economic factors that causes the academic performance for satisfactory level of proficiency. The effect of the social and economic factors are significant at .01 significant level of confidence in the regression analysis. To improve the academic performance the class advisers suggested to improve the financial assistance of the government to the school and the pupils, improve teaching resources and the parents should participate to motivate their children to improve school activities.

Conclusions

This study was conducted to investigate the effect of the socio-economic factors on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils of Port Area Elementary School. It utilized descriptive research design to explain the effect of the social and economic factors on the academic performance of the intermediate pupils. There are four designed research questions such as “What is the level of academic performance of pupil’s at Port Area Elementary School?”; “What social factors affect pupil’s academic performance at

Port Area Elementary School?"; "What economic factors affect pupil's academic performance at Port Area Elementary School?" and "What measures can be put in place to improve pupil's performance at Port Area Elementary School?" The first problem was answered using weighted mean. The second and third problems were answered using weighted mean and simple regression. The fourth problem was answered using interview.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded.

Research Agenda

1. A similar study should be conducted in the other schools or district.
2. The school administrator should consider in the program of activities anecdotal records of the pupils officially enrolled in their schools.
3. The class advisers should patronize the anecdotal records in the classroom programs and activities to enhance proper guidance of pupils in the class.
4. The guidance counselor should keep a similar anecdotal records in their offices to coordinate the parents, class advisers, and school administrator to address social problems of the pupils.
5. The class adviser should collaboratively work hand on hand with the guidance counselor, school administrator and parents to make alternative solutions to problems involving social, economic and moral problems in the school.

Policy

1. The DepEd should conduct monitorial visit quarterly to revisit the social, economic and moral values in the different schools.
2. The DepEd should conduct seminars, workshops and other similar activities to address the social, economic and moral problems of the pupils.
3. The DepEd should make a policy for timely submission of listing pupils who are under treatment of a social, economic and moral problems in the school.
4. The School Administrator should be guided with a written policy involving management of social, economic and moral problems in their schools.
5. The DepEd should establish policy to involve parental partner in case of social, economic and moral problems of the pupils in the school.

Research Problem

1. Enhancement of Social, Economic and Moral Records of the Legitimate Pupils
2. Anecdotal Records of Pupils: Its Importance in Enhancing Social, Economic and Moral Upbringing
3. Anecdotal Records of the Pupils: Its Impact on the Academic Performance
4. Measures and Proper Guidelines to Improve Academic Performance through Social, Economic and Moral Evaluation

5. Effective Approach to Improve Academic Performance: Outcome Based Records

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in compliance with ethical standards, ensuring that all procedures adhered to ethical guidelines and principles for research integrity.

REFERENCES

- Ajan, R. A., Amilhasad, A. I., Habbail, M. S., & Talikan, A. I. (2024). MOTHER TONGUE INTERFERENCE: ITS EFFECT TO THE ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION SKILLS OF BA ELS STUDENTS IN A UNIVERSITY IN SULU, PHILIPPINES. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(3), 996-1005.
- Dubey, U. K. B., & Kothari, D. P. (2022). *Research methodology: Techniques and trends*. Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Hoffman, J. A., & Miller, E. A. (2020). Addressing the consequences of school closure due to COVID-19 on children's physical and mental well-being. *World medical & health policy*, 12(3), 300-310.
- Lurie, L. A., Hagen, M. P., McLaughlin, K. A., Sheridan, M. A., Meltzoff, A. N., & Rosen, M. L. (2021). Mechanisms linking socioeconomic status and academic achievement in early childhood: Cognitive stimulation and language. *Cognitive development*, 58, 101045.
- Munir, J., Faiza, M., Jamal, B., Daud, S., & Iqbal, K. (2023). The impact of socio-economic status on academic achievement. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 3(2), 695-705.
- Ndemwa, N. M., & Ngesu, L. M. (2021). Influence of Socio-Economic Factors on Standard 8 Pupils' Academic Performance in Day Primary Schools in Mbooni West Sub-County. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 5(1), 433-436.
- Rosalina, F. (2023). Improving Teacher Performance through Self-Efficacy, Training, and Organizational Culture that Enhances Job Satisfaction. *PRODUKTIF: Jurnal Kepegawaian dan Organisasi*, 2(2), 133-144.
- Somasundaran, S. (2022). Types of Study Designs. *Kerala Journal of Ophthalmology*, 34(3), 279-282.
- Srivastava, D. A. K. (2024). *Questionnaire & Interview In Research: Tool & Technique*. Legal Research Methodology, Dr. Ashish Kumar Srivastava (Ed.), Satyam Law International, New Delhi.
- Talikan, A. I. (2021). Exploring Instructional Competencies of Mindanao State University-Sulu Teachers in the Age of COVID-19 Pandemic. *Open Access Indonesia Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(4), 364-381. <https://doi.org/10.37275/oaijss.v4i2.54>
- Talikan, A. (2022). Effectiveness of Back-to-Basic Mathematics on Physics Performance of the Students in Mindanao State University-Sulu in the Southern Philippines. *LC International Journal of STEM (ISSN: 2708-7123)*, 2(4), 7-12. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6412425>

- Tomaszewski, W., Xiang, N., & Western, M. (2020). Student engagement as a mediator of the effects of socio-economic status on academic performance among secondary school students in Australia. *British Educational Research Journal*, 46(3), 610-630.
- Vadivel, B., Alam, S., Nikpoo, I., & Ajanil, B. (2023). The impact of low socioeconomic background on a child's educational achievements. *Education Research International*, 2023(1), 6565088.